

FAAM facility for airborne atmospheric measurements

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No.: B284
Date: 18 April 2007
Take Off: 24:34:47
Landing: 30:17:55
Flight Time: 5h43m08

Campaign: IASI - ARIES

Operating Area: Ellington - Oklahoma

POB	Position	Name	Institute
1	Captain	Alan Roberts	Directflight
2	Co-pilot	Ian Ramsay-Rae	Directflight
3	CCM	Gaynor Ottaway	Directflight
4	Mission Scientist 1	Jonathan Taylor	Met Office
5	Flight Manager	Jamie Trembath	FAAM
6	Cloud Physics	Paul James	FAAM
7	Core Chem / AVAPS	Doug Anderson	FAAM
9	ARIES	Joss Kent	Met Office
10	MARSS	Chawn Harlow	Met Office
11	AMS	Will Morgan	University of Manchester
12	Wet Neph	Dave Tiddeman	Met Office
13	Mission Scientist 2	Alessio Bozzo	University of Bologna
14			
15			
16			
17			
18			
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20			

Flight Track:

B284 Track 18-APR-07

FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No B284

Date: 18/19th April 2007

Project: IASI

Location: Metop overpass, ARM site Oklahoma

Start Time	End Time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
----	----	-----	-----	---	-----
230130		Start-Up	0.11 kft	178	29'36.05N 95'10.06
242820		ASP	0.08 kft	026	open
243447		T/O	0.90 kft	031	
254436	254859	Profile 1	24.0 - 20.0 kft	333	
255005	260549	Profile 1	20.0 - 4.1 kft	335	point SOUTH
255041		QNH	19.6 kft	336	1012
260549	262918	Run 1	4.1 kft	003	point SOUTH to point NORTH
263221	264410	Profile 2	4.1 - 15.1 kft	166	interrupt
264859	265021	Profile 2	15.1 - 16.1 kft	345	interrupt
265047	265511	Profile 2	16.1 - 20.0 kft	357	interrupt
265921	270848	Profile 2	20.0 - 28.0 kft	173	
270859	271406	Run 2.1	28.0 kft	193	
271849	273735	Run 2.2	28.0 kft	349	
272010		Sonde 1	28.0 kft	350	Point SOUTH
272511		Sonde 2	28.0 kft	349	
272811		Sonde 3	28.0 kft	348	
273100		Sonde 4	28.0 kft	348	
273312		Sonde 5	28.0 kft	351	
274151	275912	Run 3	29.0 kft	178	
274151		Sonde 6	29.0 kft	178	
274406		Sonde 7	29.0 kft	203	
274700		Sonde 8	29.0 kft	195	
275000		Sonde 9	29.0 kft	193	
275301		Sonde 10	29.0 kft	192	
275600		Sonde 11	29.0 kft	192	
280317	282356	Profile 3	29.0 - 4.0 kft	001	point SOUTH to point NORTH
282712	285427	Run 4	4.0 - 4.1 kft	181	point NORTH to point SOUTH
301755		Land	0.08 kft		
302309		ASP	0.08 kft	359	Closed
302444		Shutdown	0.08 kft	359	29'36.06 N 95'10.06W

B284 Track 18-APR-07

KEFD -> KHOU - Overview

NavData Cycle 2007-3 Expired: Thursday, 12 April 2007.

Scale: 1:3871035 (1 inch = 53.09 naut mi). Printed on 18 Apr 2007

JEPPESEN

FliteStar 9.170

ARRIVS 4-22

Sortie Brief – Oklahoma

Flight B284

Wed 18th April 2007

Mission Scientist: Jonathan Taylor

Briefing: 1730L 2230Z

Take off: 1930L 0030Z

Land: 0100L 0600Z

Satellite overpass = 03:35Z

Aim: To underfly IASI on the Metop satellite in the vicinity of the ARM site coordinated with the overpass.

Location: Over ARM instrument site located near Lamont, Oklahoma.

Weather conditions: Clear skies or Broken cloud.

Key instruments: ARIES, MARSS, SWS, AVAPS, Core Chem, Cloud Phys

Fixed Points: BAe 146 to follow fixed ground positions as follows:

Over OKLAHOMA

Fixed point STH: (35°50' N, 97°36' W)

Fixed point NTH: (37°20'N, 97° 35'W)

1. Take off from Houston and transit to Oklahoma point STH to arrive at 4000ft (90 mins)
2. SLR from STH to NTH at 4000ft (25 mins)
3. Profile from NTH to STH from 4000ft to FL280 (30 mins)
4. SLR from STH to NTH at FL280 (20mins)
5. SLR from NTH to STH at FL280 (20mins) overpass occurs during this run
6. Profile from STH to NTH from FL280 to 4000ft (30mins)
7. SLR from NTH to STH at 4000ft (25mins)
8. Transit back to Houston (90mins)

Drop sonde pattern: aim is to launch sondes with good coverage along the sub-satellite track with particular density at the overpass time.

Satellite overpass – 03:35Z

Dropsonde launch:	Time Z	Time relative to overpass (mins)
#1	0325	T-10
#2	0328	T-7
#3	0331	T-4
#4	0333	T-2
#5	0341	T+6
#6	0344	T+9

Plus 4 more sondes spread evenly during other high level run.

ARIES operations

During 1st low level run, mainly NADIR with short ZEN view

During overpass run all NADIR

During other high level run mainly NADIR with short Zenith

During 2nd low level run mix of NADIR and ZEN

Sortie Brief - Oklahoma

Flight B284

Wed 18th April 2007

Mission Scientist: Jonathan Taylor

Briefing: 1730L 2230Z

Take off: 1930L 0030Z

Land: 0100L 0600Z

Plot HIGHMAN V. ALT.

*flow light on PSAP not on
@ when flow is*

Satellite overpass = 03:35Z

h - AVAPS - SNO.

Aim: To underfly IASI on the Metop satellite in the vicinity of the ARM site coordinated with the overpass.

Location: Over ARM instrument site located near Lamont, Oklahoma. 1012

Weather conditions: Clear skies or Broken cloud. m3

Key instruments: ARIES, MARSS, SWS, AVAPS, Core Chem, Cloud Phys 10

Fixed Points: BAe 146 to follow fixed ground positions as follows: 8

Over OKLAHOMA

Fixed point STH: (35°50' N, 97°36' W)

Fixed point NTH: (37°20' N, 97° 35' W)

JT says no ↑

*7.5
6.7
5.7
4.5
3.6
2.6
1.5
0.6
0.47*

1. Take off from Houston and transit to Oklahoma point STH to arrive at 4000ft (90 mins)
2. SLR from STH to NTH at 4000ft (25 mins)
3. Profile from NTH to STH from 4000ft to FL280 (30 mins)
4. SLR from STH to NTH at FL280 (20mins)
5. SLR from NTH to STH at FL280 (20mins) overpass occurs during this run
6. Profile from STH to NTH from FL280 to 4000ft (30mins)
7. SLR from NTH to STH at 4000ft (25mins)
8. Transit back to Houston (90mins)

run 3 27:41:51

Sonde 8.

- 0.47 Check

T/O → 24:34:47

LAND → 30:17:55

Sonde #s

*27:08:40
no hunks available @ this time*

CAP @ 10,000 ft.

LOOKS LIKE SONDE 7 IS THE ADDED ONE

Herman & Aires show diff surface temp →

BBa = 8-10µ

Sens to atmosphere above which is colder

Aires 2565 Super waefly

Aircraft Scientist's Log

J. TAMAR

Flight No **B. 284**
FAAM © 2004

Date 18/10/07

Page 1 of 5

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
					Test obs logs ~ script.
					3/8 Ci overhead.
24 2900					8/8 Sc below. within strip of Ci ahead otherwise clear above.
24 3400					steady at F2260. cloud breaking below and ahead.
25 07 18					still clear above clear below but broken Sc ahead.
25 13 43		F2240			cloud breaking below. still clear above.
25 35 01		F2260			clear above clear directly below and ahead broken Sc to. West.
25 45 36	P1	F2240	334		strip P1 from F2240 to 6000ft at Point South
					clear above + below.
25 48 59	P1	F2200	335		Interrupt P1 for air temp etc.
01 48 59					
25 50 05	P1	F2200	336		Restart P1 21600ft QNH 1012
01 50 05					clear skies above + below
					Baro ↑ to 800/c P. ASP.
					Now in moist biting layer but remain clear just below + above
(26 05 49)	P1-1	4000ft	003	POINT STH.	End P1 + Start P1-1 QNH 1012
02 05 49					ARRIES NADIR 266km = 285 285K
					Totally clear !!

Aircraft Scientist's Log

 Flight No **B 286**
 FAAM © 2004

 Date **18/6/07**

 Page **2** of **5**

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
261137					Upper Reynolds = 387 w/m ²
2617					Passed pt C - Area site.
262338	P1	4000ft	006		QNH 101mb. cloud base at all levels RASP ≈ 650cm ⁻³
262918 } 022918 }	P1	4000ft	003		End Run 1 at Point Nth.
263221 } 023221 }	P2 ↑	4000ft ↑	180		sky P2 ↑ 4000ft
263656					Blue. 7660ft RASP down to slight turbulence at 100/c below
264352					at Area site
264410 } 024410 }	P2	15000ft	180		Intercept P2 QNH 101mb
264859 } 024859 }	P2	15000ft ↑	366		Restart P2 ↑
265021 } 025021 }	P2	16000ft			Intercept P2 @ 16000ft QNH ¹⁰¹ 101mb
265069 } 025069 }	P2	16000ft ↑	356		Restart P2 Totally clear.
265511 } 025511 }	P2	17200ft	356		Intercept P2
265921 } 025921 }	P2	17200ft ↑	170		Restart P2

Aircraft Scientist's Log

J. Taylor

Flight No **B** 286
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Date 18/09

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
					w/BSF & wing later 70m South.
270848 } 030848 }	P2 P2.1	F280	193		Early P2 + Shaky Run 2.2
	P2.1	F280	193		End P2.1
271849 } 021849 }	P2.2	F280	352		st Run 2.2 Just from South of Pt South.
272009 } 032010 }		F280	349		Prep sonde 1. T = -36.38 Td = -55.15 286/33ms ⁻¹ .
272511 } 032511 }		F280	348		Prep sonde 2 -36.29 / -55.16C P = 329mb 287/35ms ⁻¹ 2616cm ⁻¹ = 287K Humid = 5.43 298K
272811 } 032811 }		F280	347		Prep sonde 3 -36.89 / -55.39 wind 35ms ⁻¹ / 285deg. 328mb.
273100 } 033100 }		F280	348		Prep sonde 4 -37.17 / -55.71 35ms ⁻¹ / 287deg P = 328mb
273312 } 033312 }		F280	351		Prep sonde 5 -38.09 -55.4 30ms ⁻¹ / 293 P0 = 328.
					climbing to F290

Aircraft Scientist's Log

S. Taylor

Flight No **B.28p**
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Date 18/4/09

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Note: Total wind data recorded by ANPS manually after launch can differ from those values due to bleedby

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
274251 034251	R3	F290	174		Descent 6 -40/-52.88. + Start of Run 3-1 Heading South
274334					3km/s / 285deg P=31kmb slight Landing correction
274406 034406	R3	F290	203		Descent 7 -40.3/-51.89 3km/s / 281deg P=31kmb
274700 034700	R3	F290	195		Descent 8 -39.8/-56.06 high white bands! 37m/s / 275 P=31k
274958 034958	R3	F290	194		Descent 9 -39.1/-57.37 36/277 31kmb
275300 035300	R3	F290	194		Descent 10 -38.8/-57.37 35/276° 31kmb
275600 035600	R3	F290	192		Descent 11. -38.7/-56.67 35/270° 31kmb
275912 035912	R3	F290			End of Run 3 at F290.

Aircraft Scientist's Log

S. Taylor

Flight No **B...286**

Date ...18/6/07.....

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
280317 040317	P3	~290	000		Start P3 ↓ from Sth point still cloud free.
280356 040356	P3	400ft	004		End P3 P=102mb At Nth point long to run South of 400ft 11.1K °C / 509 ft. P=873mb
280712 040712	R4	400ft	178		Stg R4 from Nth to Sth Ozone data all looks rubbish! PCASP = 650cm ⁻³
285627 0405627	R4	400ft	178		End R4 at Sth point. Changing to recover to Ellington.

CLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG

Flight number: B284 **T/O:** 243447
Date of flight: 18/4/07 **Land:** 301755

A) FFSSP PROCESSING		
Processing Stage	Done?	Comments
1) Transfer *.txt files from DVD to processing PC Bnnn_FFSSP_hh.txt for each hour of data Bnnn_FFSSP_HVMS.txt	NO	hh = Last sec processed =
2) FTP the files (ascii) from the PC to directory PMSDATA: on FLOODS		File size =
3) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.FAST_FSSP]FFSSP_EXTRACT_TAS a) Flight number: Bnnn b) Path name: MFDDATA:Bnnn_MFDX c) Output directory: PMSDATA: d) Start time: <i>0 if unknown (see comment box)</i> e) End time: <i>240000 if unknown</i>		Use time just before/after take-off/landing. If T/O /landing just after/before the hour, ensure start/end time is before/after the hour if there is an FFSSP_hh.txt file for that hour.
4) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.FAST_FSSP]FFSSP_PROCESS_TXT a) Flight number: Bnnn b) Directory: PMSDATA: c) TAS in processing: Y d) Vel threshold (clicks) 0 e) Calibration file: <i>Use the most recent calibration file.</i> Format FFSSP_CALddmmyyyy.txt Calibration files to be stored in MRFB:[PMS.FAST_FSSP] f) Adjust FFSSP time Y/N g) If Y, enter value to add to data time (seconds)		Total glitches = Sec file written ok? Note calibration file used Yes only if gross errors occur in FFSSP time eg; ~ 1hour
5) FLOODS> WAVE a) WAVE> write_procffssp_to_m5,'pmsdata:Bnnn_procffssp.dat', 'mfddata:Bnnn_mfdX','pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procffssp',/auto b) WAVE> exit		Use PVWAVE for this section Note time correction applied to FFSSP by /auto =
6) FLOODS> MODIFY a) Modifying datasets: pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procffssp b) Dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdX c) New dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdY (y=x+1) d) Parameter description file: <i>leave blank to use default</i>		Input file size = M5 output file size =
7) CHECKS: i). Are FFSSP and JW/Nevzorov LWC synchronized in time? <i>In flight_plot, parameters</i> <i>JW LWC para 535</i> <i>Nevzorov LWC para 602</i> <i>FFSSP LWC para 1202</i> ii). If not, repeat from step 5b replacing /auto with addt=x which adds x+20 secs to FFSSP time.		Synchronized?

CLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG

Flight number: B284 **T/O:** 243447 = 003447
Date of flight: 18/4/07 **Land:** 301755 = 061755

B) 2D PROCESSING		REPROCESS +1hr
Processing Stage	Done?	Comments
1) Transfer Bnnn.dat file from CD/DVD to PC	Y	
2) Zip up file on PC (Bnnn.zip)	Y	
3) FTP the zipped file (binary) from the PC to the directory SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA] on FLOODS	y	Via BADC
4) Log on to FLOODS		
5) Unzip SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA]Bnnn.zip	y	Size of Bnnn.dat =
6) FLOODS> WAVE WAVE> CONVERT_SEADAS_FILE a) Input file: SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA]Bnnn.dat b) Output file: SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA]Bnnn_seadas.dat WAVE> exit		Use PVWAVE for this section Blocks read = 47373 Blocks written = 47373 Bad reads =0
7) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.SEADAS]READM200_FILE a) Default directory: PMSDATA: b) Flight number: Bnnn c) Disk file name: SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA] Bnnn_seadas.dat d) Comment string: e) Start time: <i>0 if unknown (T/O – 5 min)</i> f) End time: <i>240000 if unknown (Land + 5 min)</i> g) Read 2DC: Y h) Read 2DP: Y i) Secondary data: Y j) FSP-SYNC: Y k) cmd.str: Y l) Auto time correction: N m) Full length secondary: N	y	Start = 003400 End = 061800 Ignore error message scroll (vestigial error from tapes) Are FRW, FSP, IMB, PCA,SEC files in PMSDATA? Are they non-zero in size?
8) FLOODS> WAVE i). WAVE> imagedisplay a) 2D directory name: PMSDATA: b) Flight number: Bnnn c) Time from IWC plot: N d) Select probe: (1) 2DC (2) 2DP e) Start time: <i>As in 7e above</i> f) End time: <i>As in 7f above</i> g) Time interval (sec): 5 recommended (0 for all images) ii). WAVE> auto_image a) 2D directory name: PMSDATA: b) Flight number: Bnnn c) Enter date: YYYYMMDD d) Enter start time: <i>0 if unknown (T/O – 1 min)</i> e) Enter end time: <i>240000 if unknown (Land – 1 min)</i> f) Enter time interval (sec) between successive imaged blocks: 10 iii). WAVE> exit to create files iv). FTP ascii *.PS files from PMSDATA: to PC v). Load each into Ghostview or other pdf-converter vi). Output as pdf file (720 dpi resolution), appending name prefix of	No Cloud n	2D image display and printing Must be done from FLOODS itself. Note any problems with images Prepare imagery for Core data From own PC again Start = End = FAAM_YYYYMMDD_R0_ Bnnn_2Dx-images.ps Notes on this in instructions

CORE-CLOUD-PHY_ to converted files		
9) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.SPEC2D.AUTO]PROCESS2D_AUTO	n	NB. an error message may appear, floating point exception, rerun and use time quoted in error message, repeat until successful.
a) Flight number: Bnnn b) Directory: PMSDATA: c) File generation: <i>Hit enter</i> d) Time correction: <i>Time offset of the 2D data</i> e) TAS: Y f) MFD directory: MFDDATA:Bnnn_MFDX g) Probe number: (1) 2DC (2) 2DP (0) Both <i>0 unless either probe known to be faulty</i> h) Start time: <i>0 if unknown (T/O + 30sec)</i> i) End time: <i>240000 if unknown (Land – 30sec)</i> j) Nominal averaging: 0.2 seconds for conversion to M5 k) Particle type 2DC: 8 if known to be in ice cloud 11 if known to be in water cloud l) Particle type 2DP: 8 if known to be in mixed-phase 8 if unknown m) Coefficient choice: 2 n) Output root filename: PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROC2D		X = Start = End = Time data processed to = 2dproc files present? *.2dc, *.2dp and *.dat
10) FLOODS> WAVE i) WAVE> WRITE_PROC2D_TO_M5, 'PMSDATA:BNNN_PROC2D.DAT', 'PMSDATA:BNNN_M5PROC2D' ii). exit	n	Use PVWAVE for this section Error message about HDDR file should be ignored. Records =
11) FLOODS> MODIFY a) Modifying datasets: pmsdata:Bnnn_m5proc2D b) Datset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdX c) New dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdY d) Parameter description file: leave blank to use default	N	X = Y = (X+1)
12) CHECKS: Are 2DC/2DP IWC of comparable magnitude and well-correlated with Nevzorov TWC? <i>In flight_plot, parameters</i> <i>Nevzerov TWC para 605</i> <i>2DC IWC para 1302</i> <i>2DP IWC para 1312</i>	n	Correlated?

CLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG

Flight number: B284 **T/O:** 243447 = 003447
Date of flight: 18/4/07 **Land:** 301755 = 061755

C) PCASP PROCESSING		
Processing Stage	Done?	Comments
1) Complete stage 7) in 2D processing Ensures Bnnn_FSP.DAT containing raw PCASP data is written to directory PMSDATA:	y	
2) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.PCASP]PROCPCASP_NEW a) Flight number: Bnnn b) File name: PMSDATA:Bnnn_FSP.DAT c) Root output name: PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROCPCASP Produces PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROCPCASP.DAT (binary) PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROCPCASP.OUT (ascii) d) Minimum size channel: <i>default = 1</i> <i>If smallest size channel are known to be noisy the value of the highest noise free channel to be entered here</i> e) Calibration volume flow rate: <i>Use the most recent value. 1.8ccs⁻¹</i> <i>Calibration files to be stored in Exeter</i> <i>Entering zero gives default value = 1.0 cm³s⁻¹</i> f) Time correction: <i>Same value as used in 2D processing stage 9d</i> g) Start time: <i>0 if unknown</i> h) End time: <i>240000 if unknown</i>		Min size = 1 Vol flow rate = 1.0
3) FLOODS> WAVE i).WAVE> write_procpcasp_to_m5, 'pmsdata:Bnnn_procpcasp.dat', 'pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procpcasp' ii). WAVE> exit		Use PVWAVE for this section
4) FLOODS> MODIFY a) Modifying datasets: pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procpcasp b) Dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdX c) New dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdY d) Parameter description file: <i>leave blank to use default</i>	n	Data not added to mfda Seadas time 0035h – 0618h Horace time 2200 h- 3029h
5) CHECKS Are PCASP and NEPH peaks synchronous? <i>In flight_plot, parameters</i> <i>Neph total blue scatter</i> <i>PCASP conc para 1550</i>	n	

FAAM Dropsonde Flight Log

Flight No.	B284	Date	18-19 Apr 2007 (sondes launched on 19 th , Z time)
Page No.	1 of 1	Operator	Doug Anderson

GMT	Sonde No.	Event	Comments
		<i>e.g. launch, splashdown</i>	<i>e.g. wind data? PTH data? Lat/Long NB strings of dropsonde data contain: time, pressure hPa, T deg C, RH %, wind direction deg, wind speed m/s, longitude, latitude, height m</i>
03:20:12	1	Launch	330.64 -14.64 0.68 297.93 32.57 -0.01 -97.599199 35.832952
03:30:10	1	land	-97.535085 35.822027
03:26:59	2	Launch	420.04 -22.79 3.33 292.75 19.60 -15.35 -97.561204 36.253921
03:35:22	2	land	-97.528354 36.251668
03:28:15	3	Launch	129.03 99.00 46.02 206.68 61.29 -0.01 -97.592633 36.517287
03:34:18	3	land	-97.553539 36.511932 (last reading at 03:33:41)
03:31:03	4	Launch	9999.00 99.00 999.00 193.20 107.28 -0.02 -97.589183 36.761544
03:41:04	4	land	972.50 17.17 59.96 269.65 5.29 -0.81 -97.535071 36.756148
03:33:14	5	Launch	-97.586723 36.953162
03:43:28	5	land	-97.536115 36.947727
03:41:52	6	Launch	315.46 -12.96 1.09 292.65 40.91 0.17 -97.599275 37.425568
03:50:36	6	land	-97.547405 37.411056 at 03:46:11 Very poor GPS data 471.50 mb
03:44:05	7	Launch	315.21 -9.54 0.78 311.65 40.77 0.00 -97.571433 37.217767
03:54:10	7	land	967.13 16.65 67.23 256.75 2.85 -6.23 -97.515987 37.214571
03:47:01	8	Launch	9999.00 99.00 999.00 237.77 32.73 0.03 -97.586431 36.952095
03:53:13	8	land	-97.554430 36.945358
03:50:03	9	Launch	-97.590590 36.683987
04:00:03	9	land	-97.529221 36.677473
03:53:04	10	Launch	-97.592689 36.416558
04:02:57	10	land	-97.527611 36.409451
03:56:03	11	Launch	-97.596710 36.144004
04:06:33	11	land	-97.525089 36.135710

ARIES flight log

Flight: B284

page 1 of

Date: 14/4/07

Operator(s): Joss

Res: 1

Gain A: 2 B?

Loc./Notes: 18/4 → 19/4 overnight IASI flight

Scans: either "[IGMs]X[co-adds]", or "[stop DRS time]" if in start/stop, or "[macro name]". View: mirror angle.

DRS time	Flt ptrn	Scans	View	Shtr	HBB	CBB	Comments
0:1325	Grnd						Skipped housekeeping
0:1503	Grnd	1	60		70.92	33.65	Grnd cal.
010628	Transit	1/60	cal	clsd	70.89	33.69	Cal
013719	Transit	1/60	cal	clsd	70.93	33.37	
020600		1/60	cal	clsd			CAL
020737	Run 1	600/1	clsd	Nov	70.92	30.40	Smear Noel. T
021233	u u	1/60	clsd	cal			
021806	u u	120/1	open	Zen			2man Zen
021906	u u	120/1	clsd	Nov	70.99	31.30	2man Noel.
021621	u u	60/1	cal	clsd	70.77	30.68	
021737	u u	600/1	Nov	clsd	70.87	30.66	Smear Noel.
022237	u u	1/60	cal	clsd	70.78	30.49	Cal.
022352	u u	120/1	Nov	clsd	70.93	30.94	2man Noel
022309	u u	120/1	Zen	open	70.33	30.71	2man Zen
022602	u u	120/1	Nov	clsd	70.89	31.33	2man Noel.
022716	u u	60/1	cal	clsd	71.06	30.92	Cal.
022934	u u	60/1	Nov	clsd	70.62	30.59	1man Noel.
023042							
023256	Profile			open			Profile Zen Hor Cald Noel Cold Hor
023452	u			open			u u u
023810	u			u			u u u
024019	u			u			u u u
024214	u			u			u u u
024413	Profile	1/60	cal	clsd			Proper cal in interrupt
024940	u u		Prof	open			Restarted Profile ZHC NCH
025049	u u		u u	u u			" " " "
025248	u u		u u	u u			" " " "
025445	u u		u u	u u			" " " "
025643	u u		u u	u u			" " " "
025923	u u		u u	u u			Restarted Profile. Profile ZHC NCH
030130	u u		Prof	u u			" "

ARIES flight log

Flight: B284

page 2 of

Date: 18/01/07

Operator(s): Joss

Res: 1

Gain A: 2 B: 2

Loc./Notes: IASL HOUSTON NIGHT OVERPASS

Scans: either "[IGMs]X[co-adds]", or "[stop DRS time]" if in start/stop, or "[macro name]". View: mirror angle.

DRS time	Fit ptrn	Scans	View	Shttr	HBB	CBB	Comments
030333	Prople2		Prog	open	66.3	3070	Prople ZHCNCH
030556	u u		u u	u u	68.3	30.6	(u - u -)
030910	u u		u u	u u	65.09	30.44	
031010	Run2-1		Cal	clsd	64.87	29.81	70.49°C on HBB view.
031142	Run2-1	120/1	Nod	clsd	70.95	30.67	2-min back down
031254	u u	1/60	Cal	clsd	70.87	30.30	Cal.
031459	Run2-2	1/60	Cal	clsd	70.80	31.56	"
031720	u 2-3	600/1	Nod	clsd	70.68	29.98	Skewed before F2280
032358	u u	1/60	Cal	clsd	70.61	30.03	Cal
032458	u u	600/1	Nod	clsd	70.7	30.58	Nod view swms
32959	u u	1/60	Cal	clsd	70.65	30.17	Cal.
033122	u u	600/1	Nod	clsd	71.27	30.46	Nod view Swd Wae 0355Z.
033622	u u	1/60	Cal	clsd	70.72	30.52	Cal.
034104	Run3	1/60	Cal	clsd	70.68	30.60	Cal.
034226	u u	600/1	Nod	clsd	70.86	30.18	Nod swms
034727	u u	1/60	Cal	open	70.70	30.56	
034830	u u	120/1	Zen	open	70.44	30.56	2-min Zen view
035008	u u	300/1	Nod	clsd	70.03	30.48	3-min Nod view
035309	u u	1/60	Cal	clsd	70.69	30.23	Cal.
035429	u u	600/1	Nod	clsd	70.62	30.33	Nod view swms
035927	u u	1/60	Cal	clsd	70.80	30.68	Cal
040631	Prople3			open			Prople ZHCNCH
040854	u u			u u			u u u u
041054	u u			u u	63.74	31.06	u u u u
041334	u u			u u			
041514	u u			u u	61.09	31.42	
041723	u u			u u	62.65	31.38	
041948	u u			u u	64.05	31.36	
042453	Run4	1/60	Cal	clsd	70.70	30.32	Cal
042641	u u	300/1	Zen	open	70.17	30.48	2-Swms Zen view
042914	u u	300/1	Nod	clsd	71.01	30.50	2-Swms Nod view

Microwave Radiometers FLIGHT LOG		Date	18/04/07	Flight	B284	log pages
Operator(s)	Chawn Harlow		Campaign	JIAVEX		
Departure	Ellington		Arrival	Ellington		

**System start
MARSS**

Visual pod inspection						•
Close 3 SSP circuit breakers						•
Close all MARSS circuit breakers						•
FERA on					at time	2218
Temperature controller initial temps	Ch16	°C	Ch	°C	Ch18	°C
Temperature controller set points		54°C	17	58°C	-20	40°C
MARSS CPU on					at time	
Initial target temperatures	Hot	297	Cold	297		
Target heating						•
*** CHECK SCAN HEAD CLEAR ***						•
Scanning on (LMD box)					at time	2219
Scan indication	Monitor			•	Visual	

Deimos

Close all Deimos circuit breakers	NOT OPERATED					
Turn on Deimos CPU						
*** CHECK SCAN HEAD CLEAR ***						
Start Deimos Software					at time	
Initial target temperatures	Hot		Cold			
Target heating						•
Scan indication	Monitor			•	Visual	
Weather	Cloud		Precip			
	Surface		Pressure			
	Other					

System functionality check (after initial system warmup, approx 1 hour)

PC to DRS Time error	$t_{PC}=t_{DRS} +$	2 sec	at time	22:50:32		
Brightness temps 'sensible'						•
Target temps	MARSS:	Hot	344.5	Cold	296.8	
	Deimos:	Hot		Cold		
Channel gains 'sensible'	Ch1 A	Ch3 A	Ch1 B	Ch3 B		
	(-)	(-)	(-)	(-)		
	Ch16	Ch17	Ch18	Ch19	Ch20	
	(40-44)	(45-49)	(40-44)	(40-44)	(44-48)	
	41.5	32.6	38.6	39.1	42.3	

Power changeover

Headset on before start						•
Listen to engine start sequence	4, 3, 2, 1.					•
LMD off (3 switches, bottom to top)						•
Exit Deimos Software (x)						
POWER CHANGEOVER						
LMD on (3 switches, top to bottom)	then pushbutton					•
Restart Deimos Software						
System running again					at time	00:25:29

Flight:

B284

KEY

- Not Fitted
- Fitted, Not Operated
- Duff Data
- Minor Problems
- OK

Thermometers

- Cabin Temperature:
- Heimann:
- Deiced Temp:
- Non-deiced Temp:

Hygrometers

- FWVS:
- General Eastern:
- Johnson Williams:
- Nezvorov:
- Total Water Probe:

Cameras

- Downward Facing:
- Forward Facing:
- Rearward Facing:
- Upward Facing:

Navigation + Aircraft

- Cruciform GPS:
- GIN Applanix:
- INU Honeywell:
- Radar Altimeter:
- RVSM IAS:
- RVSM Static Pressure:
- XR5 GPS:

Report Created 26/06/2007
15:34:14

Misc Core

- AMTG:
- AVAPS:
- Cabin Pressure:
- Fax machine:
- Printer:
- S9 Static Pressure:
- Satcom C:
- Satcom H:
- Turb Centre-Static:
- Turb Left Right:
- Turb Up-Down:
- Turb Horizontal Chk:
- Turb Vertical Chk:
- Weather Radar:
- DLUs:**
- DLU AERACK:
- DLU BBR Lower:
- DLU BBR Upper:
- DLU Core Chem:
- DLU Core Consoles:
- DLU Port Aft:
- DLU Port Fwd:
- DLU Stbd Fwd:

Radiometers

- Lower:**
- BBR (clear) Lower:
- BBR (IR) Lower:
- BBR (red) Lower:
- Upper:**
- BBR (clear) Upper:
- BBR (IR) Upper:
- BBR (red) Upper:
- ARIES:
- DEIMOS:
- IR Camera:
- JNO2 Lower:
- JNO2 Upper:
- JO1D Lower:
- JO1D Upper:
- MARSS:
- SHIMS Lower:
- SHIMS Upper:
- SWS:
- TAFTS:

Last Updated:

Cloud Probes

- 2DC:
- 2DP:
- FFSSP:
- PCASP:
- ADA:
- CCN:
- CDP:
- CIP 100:
- CIP 25:
- CPI:
- CVI:
- SID1:
- SID2:
- Aerosol**
- CPC 3025A:
- Filters 47mm:
- Filters 90mm:
- Neph - Dry:
- Neph - Wet:
- PSAP:
- AMS:
- CPC 3025 (AMS):
- INC:
- VACC:
- CPC 3010A (CVI):

20/04/2007 17:28:42

Chemistry

- CO Aerolaser 5002:
- NOx TE42C:
- Ozone TE49C:
- Ozone TE49:
- SO2 TE43C:
- TDLAS (NIR) CH4:
- TDLAS (NIR) CO2:
- FAGE:
- Formaldehyde:
- NOxy:
- ORAC:
- PAN:
- PERCA:
- Peroxide:
- PTRMS:
- TDLAS (1C):
- WAS Bags:
- WAS Bottles:
- Misc Non-Core**
- CASI/ATM:
- LIDAR:
- LTI:
- SAW Hygrometer:

Faults / Incidents Log

Flight No. B284

Date: 18 April 2007

Instruments

1. No a/c data getting to AVAPS
2. Problem with final Heiman Cal
3. No O3 data, low flows on instrument
4. Marrs channel 16
5. Satcom phone still not a big fan of the USA

Aircraft

Nil

Satcom-H Calls

Nil

Post Flight - Turb Probe Water Traps

1. Indicate Amount of Water: a) Nil b) 1-2 drops c) ¼ full or more d) Ice present
2. Emptied by:
3. Dried by:

Pre-Flighter's Log

Date: 18-APR-07

Flight No: B284

Pre-Flighter: Bob Wells

<u>Item</u>	<u>✓ or x</u>	<u>Location</u>	<u>Action</u>	<u>Comments</u>
1	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Hangar	Collect Dustbin, put on a/c	
		<u>Aircraft Cabin</u>		
2	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Core Chemistry	Gases x 3 ON	
3	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Cabin	All Racks Checked	
4	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Fwd CorCon	All reqd CBs made	
5	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Aft CorCon	CBs made, PCs ON	
6	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	HORACE	Optical Disk loaded	Old disk removed from drive unlabelled
7	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	HORACE	Recording data	
8	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	HORACE	DLU Status Checked	
9	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	HORACE	HORACE Status Checked	
10	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Satcom H	Power LED ON	Fault report with Stratos
11	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Nevzorov	Checked and OFF	
12	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	GPS	Checked	
13	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	INU	Align	
14	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Cameras Pictures	Checked x 4 OK	
15	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Core Chemistry	Instruments Checked OK	
16	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Core Chemistry	CO Flows Checked OK	
17	<input type="checkbox"/>	FWVS	Set up	
18	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Video x 2	Records okay, Rewind	Night Flight
19	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Delced Rosemount	Heater Checked / Set	
20	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Heimann	Calibration Checked	
21	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	TWC	ON & Checked	
22	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	GE	Balance checked	
23	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	INU	Navigate then back to Align	
24	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Hubs x 4	Checked ON	
25	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Fwd Console	Miss. Sci Laptop CB made	& CB on Port Fwd SSP
26	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	CNC	Butanol filled	AMS bags
27	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	CGPS	Set up	
28	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Miss. Sci Laptop	Checked Onboard	
	<input type="checkbox"/>			
	<input type="checkbox"/>			
	<input type="checkbox"/>			

External Checks overleaf →

Pre-Flighter's Log

<u>Item</u> ✓ or x	<u>Location</u>	<u>Action</u>	<u>Comments</u>
<u>External</u>			
29	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Turb Probe	Clean if reqd, Photo taken	
30	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> JW	Cleaned & Checked	
31	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> DI Rosemount	Cleaned & Checked	
32	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> NDI Rosemount	Cleaned & Checked	
33	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Nevzorov	Cleaned/windings checked	
34	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> GE	Cleaned & Checked	
35	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Lower BBRs	Domes cleaned/checked	
36	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Camera Windows	Cleaned	
37	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Heimann	Lens checked OK	
38	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> TWC Cover	Fitted if required	
39	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> All other covers	Removed	
40	<input type="checkbox"/> Dustbin	Returned to hangar	
41	<input type="checkbox"/> Tools	Check ALL in Toolkit	
42	<input type="checkbox"/> Tools	Avalon informed	
<u>Avalon Checks</u>			
43	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Upper BBRs Checked & Cleaned		Signed
44	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> ICEX applied		
45	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Traps empty (weekly only)		

MISSING LOG SHEETS:

The following log sheets are not available for flight B284:

Log	Reason
De-brief	Sortie De-brief yet to be created by Jon Taylor
Core Chemistry	no In Flight log except in cases of instrument problems
PSAP	No log appears to have been taken for this flight
FWVS	No log is taken for this FWVS
AMS	Log only of interest to instrument operator so no copy left with FAAM

Document control

Revision	Date	Author	Comments
r0	12 Nov 2007	Doug Anderson	Initial version missing the above noted logs
r1			
r2			

VIDEO RECORDINGS:

No Digital8 video recordings were made on this flight

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New plot, same times

Flight B284 28:34:20

Heading 178 deg Speed 217 knots Height 4.0kft Press 873mb

Lat 36°54.0'N Long 97°30.0'W Wind 7 ms-1/ 152 deg

Temp 10.87C Dewpoint 5.79C

From 24:36:10 to now

Current values			
— TIME FROM MIDNIGHT	102858	secs	● All
— HEIMAN SURFACE TEMP	10.65	deg C	○

New plot, same times

Flight B284 28:31:15

Heading 177 deg Speed 219 knots Height 4.0kft Press 873mb

Lat 37°6.0'N Long 97°30.0'W Wind 7 ms-1/ 153 deg

Temp 10.97C Dewpoint 5.72C

From 24:36:10 to now

Current values			
— TIME FROM MIDNIGHT	102675	secs	● All
— HEIMAN SURFACE TEMP	9.55	deg C	○

Flight B284 28:56:42

Heading 184 deg Speed 274 knots Height 8.6kft Press 733mb

Lat 35°36.0'N Long 97°36.0'W Wind 9 ms-1/ 305 deg

Temp 6.82C Dewpoint -10.76C

From 26:05:58 to 28:54:48

Current values
HEIMAN SURFACE TEMP 8.31 deg C All
PRESSURE HEIGHT 8.67 Kft

New plot, same times

Flight B284 28:32:13

Heading 179 deg Speed 218 knots Height 4.0kft Press 873mb

Lat 37°6.0'N Long 97°30.0'W Wind 7 ms-1/ 155 deg

Temp 10.89C Dewpoint 5.97C

From 24:36:10 to now

Current values
TIME FROM MIDNIGHT 102732 secs All
HEIMAN SURFACE TEMP 8.6 deg C

Flight B284 27:52:00

Heading 193 deg Speed 326 knots Height 29.0kft Press 314mb

Lat 36°24.0'N Long 97°36.0'W Wind 36 ms-1/ 275 deg

Temp -38.78C Dewpoint -57.84C

From 26:32:58 to 27:08:48

Current values
PRESSURE HEIGHT 8846.07 m All
OZONE MIXING RATIO 10.29 ppb

New plot, same times

Flight B284 26:26:03

Heading 3 deg Speed 222 knots Height 4.0kft Press 873mb

Lat 37°0.0'N Long 97°30.0'W Wind 7 ms-1/ 123 deg

Temp 11.0C Dewpoint 5.78C

From 24:00:58 to now

Current values				
—	TIME FROM MIDNIGHT	95163	secs	<input checked="" type="radio"/> All
—	LOWER PYRANOMETER CLEAR FLUX	-1.3	W m-2	<input type="radio"/>
—	LOWER PYRANOMETER RED FLUX	4.12	W m-2	<input type="radio"/>
—	LOWER PYRGEOMETER FLUX	412.12	W m-2	<input type="radio"/>

New plot, same times

Flight B284 28:39:51

Heading 179 deg Speed 218 knots Height 4.0kft Press 873mb

Lat 36°36.0'N Long 97°30.0'W Wind 6 ms-1/ 153 deg

Temp 10.61C Dewpoint 5.49C

From 24:00:58 to now

Current values				
—	TIME FROM MIDNIGHT	103191	secs	● All
—	LOWER PYRANOMETER CLEAR FLUX	0.59	W m-2	⌋
—	LOWER PYRANOMETER RED FLUX	1.47	W m-2	⌋
—	LOWER PYRGEOMETER FLUX	409.43	W m-2	⌋